

Self-Reflection Tool

The self-reflection tool was developed by Ecsite, Ars Electronica, and MUSEUM BOOSTER in the framework of DOORS – Digital Incubator for Museums.

The team:

*Pablo Bes Alonso, Ana-Maria Carabelea, Stephanos Cherouvis, Vanessa Hanneschläger,
Veronika Liebl, Olga Tykhonova, Pere Vilanova*

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www.norder.gr

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Instructions Booklet

This instruction booklet accompanies a self-reflection tool in the form of a card deck. A printable version of the card deck can be found at the end of this document.

The card deck facilitates a self-reflection exercise designed to help teams understand the digital maturity levels of their organisation and map out ways to improve their current paradigm. The questions encourage an in-depth reflection on the status-quo and potential enablers and blockers within an organisation as a first step towards formulating more sustainable digital strategies.

The exercise can involve the entire team, a few staff members or be done individually. However, multiple perspectives on the activities, structure and approaches can create a more accurate picture of an organisation's digital maturity. Each question is an opportunity for participants to bring examples, personal experiences and views to form and inform a bigger picture. Thus, participants should be encouraged to be as detailed and as brave as possible in their reflection.

The self-reflection exercise is divided into five sections

STRATEGY

INNOVATION

OPENNESS

ORGANISATION

SKILLS

Clarifications are provided in short paragraphs that set the context, as well as tips on how to approach certain guiding questions and angles one might consider. The workshop lead should familiarise themselves with these beforehand, to better guide the participants.

The tool is non-linear and non-hierarchical. All five categories are equally relevant to the exercise, and as such, there is no prescribed pathway. Start with what makes the most sense for your team. On the back of each card, you will also find connected questions in other categories. You can skip to the questions in those categories, if this makes sense for you and your team.

Practical Tips

Before the Workshop

1. Carefully consider and identify the most relevant participants from your team and invite them to take part.
2. Set aside a few hours for the self-reflection exercise and make sure you plan breaks.
3. Print the cards in advance.
Note: *Some main questions are linked to other questions. This information is on the back of each card.*
4. Make as many copies as needed depending on the number of participants.
5. The main questions are contextualised and some guiding questions are accompanied by further tips to help the workshop lead introduce them and give participants a starting point in the self-reflection exercise. You can read them aloud or use them as inspiration to build your own explanation for each question.

Practical Tips During the Workshop

1. Present the agenda for the day and introduce the participants to the self-reflection tool.
2. Start with whichever section makes most sense for your team. When in doubt, you can introduce the categories and have a quick vote on which section to begin with.
3. Once you've decided on the starting point in your self-reflection, hand out the printed question cards and sticky notes for participants to write down their answers.
4. If you have a large group of participants, we recommend you divide them into smaller groups and ask them to collectively reflect on the questions.
5. We recommend giving participants a time limit to answer each of the main questions, including the time spent answering the guiding questions. Participants should write down their answers on sticky notes.
6. Next, participants compare answers and discuss their views on the question. We recommend you allocate 15 min. for the discussion following each of the questions.
7. During the discussion, gather the answers and the main points of the group discussions on a whiteboard or in an online document. This way the team has something they can go back to after the workshop.

Practical Tips

After the Workshop

1. Document the shared reflection. If you used a whiteboard during the workshop, transfer everything into an online document and share it with the participants.
2. You can organise another self-reflection exercise in six-months' time and compare how the answers about certain organisational aspects may have changed.

Setting the tone

As you guide participants through the self-reflection exercise, some questions will seem trickier than others. If organisations are not far along in the process of developing a digital strategy, their staff members might not be able to answer some of the questions. In these cases, instead of reflecting on previous experiences, participants should be encouraged to explore how they would approach the different dimensions of a digital strategy within their organisations.

*Questions like **‘How is the digital strategy used and by whom?’** will become **‘How would the digital strategy be used and by whom?’***

Strategy

Question 1

How does your organisation develop digital strategies to contribute to its overall transformation?

This question links to

Q1 Organisation

Q2 Skills

Q1 Openness

Q1 Innovation

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

An organisation's digital transformation and maturity are best supported by a digital strategy aligned with its overall mission and values. A good example of that is a social media strategy that does not focus only on boosting online presence but serves a bigger goal - be that to negotiate the organisation's role in the community, communicate its values, contribute to greater objectives related to cultural heritage, understanding past narratives and events, understanding and caring about audiences, etc.

Such strategies should focus on the digital inclusion and empowerment of staff and engage actors and stakeholders within and beyond the organisation. They can often include other aspects such as budget allocation and opportunities for Continuing Professional Development – in this case, engaging as many staff members as possible enables an organisation to address multiple, diverse needs.

Finally, the assessment and refinement of any strategy should place emphasis on both short and long-term goals.

Strategy

Question 1 Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. Who was involved in setting up a digital strategy for your organisation?
2. How is the digital strategy used, and by whom?

Tip (Q1 & Q2): If the organisation doesn't yet have a digital strategy participants should think about how they would set one up and who they would involve in the process.

3. What is the focus of your digital strategy? Why?

Tip: Discuss which areas were or will be covered in the strategy, and which ones still need to be developed. Examples of such areas are preservation and archiving, exhibition and content production, operations, marketing, outreach and engagement, business modeling. Discuss also how digital tools can help reach institutional goals.

Strategy

Question 1 Guiding questions

4. How is the digital strategy designed in terms of objectives, planning, and actions?
5. How is the digital strategy designed in terms of decision-making and allocating resources?

Tip: Participants should think about how and who (from leadership to museum practitioners) executes or will execute the actions derived from the strategy and, if applicable, how briefing and reporting is or will be done.

6. What is the time span of your digital strategy, and how often is it revised?

Tip: The assessment and measurement process can include defining relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) for each planned action, defining the purpose of measuring, assessment cycles and frequency and the action taken if KPIs are not met. If there were revisions, discuss what you have learned as a team and how the changes needed were introduced and accepted.

Strategy

Question 2

How does your organisation identify the biggest challenges to boosting digital maturity?

This question links to

Q1 Organisation

Q1 Skills

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

Pinpointing the actual challenges and blockers to a healthy digital development is not an easy task. Organisations, especially small museums or museums with a long history, often point to superficial or generic reasons, such as a particular mindset of the staff (usually attributed to years in service), lack of funding, internal politics, etc. Undoubtedly, these factors underlie most stalemate situations, but uncovering all the complexities and particularities of the challenges by engaging with people and structures is key to overcoming them.

Strategy

Question 2 Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. What are the steps in identifying challenges to digital maturity?

Tip: Discuss how the organization's approach to understanding and overcoming challenges could be enriched. Here it might help to think about potential overlooked challenges, such as a tendency for short-term thinking, the issue of legacy structures, technology resistance and fears, as well as missing data and audience information necessary to advance digital maturity, for e.g., data on collection, programme, finance, marketing, commercial, HR, societal.

2. What tools or processes do you use to identify challenges?

Tip: Some examples of tools or processes are working documents, informal group exchanges, workshops, etc.

Strategy

Question 2 Guiding questions

3. Who is involved in setting up, running and revising the process of identifying challenges?

Tip: Some examples of actors who could be involved in setting up, running and revising the process are staff members or external consultants, experts, partners.

4. Which external factors do you perceive as threatening and/or enabling digital maturity?

Strategy

Question 3

What are some IT and digital standards used in your organisation?

This question links to

Q2 Skills

Q2 Innovation

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

An IT Standard is a rule, principle, technique, process or template designed to provide consistency to the planning, development, operation, and governance of Information Technology services. Such standards enable devices to communicate with one another, facilitating the exchange of information and describing security procedures. Internal standards, policies and processes must comply with existing legislation. Museums that process and store audience data need standards (or other professional practices) on how to manage and safeguard the data and compliance with the law must be ensured throughout the museum and by all employees. Sharing standards and policies within the organisation helps improve both the organisational performance, and the interoperability of different systems.

Strategy

Question 3 Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. How are IT services managed?

Tip: Think of the physical or digital infrastructures that enable the delivery of IT services (including cloud-based services) in your organisation. Some ways of managing IT services can include ensuring service accessibility, providing maintenance training to staff, or offering help desk services and IT service monitoring, maintenance, and recovery. A data management plan and/or internal IT policies can cover GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), online privacy, data security, copyright law, social media usage policies, open access policies, etc.

2. How does your organisation ensure secure data management?

Tip: Secure data management is essential across the board, from collection, encryption, processing, storing, backing-up, to sharing and/or archiving. Some examples of the type of data managed that are typically of interest for the operation of museums can include the digital aspects of fundraising, digital sales, compatibility of specialized data such as 3D digitized data, etc.

Strategy

Question 3 Guiding questions

3. Do you follow metadata standards, and if not, why?

Tip: *If you don't follow metadata standards, think about whether there are metadata standards in the sector and what would be the first steps in adopting them.*

4. Which standards do you deem essential for future digital products or services?

Innovation

Question 1

How does your organisation create additional impact, reach, and returns through digital innovation?

This question links to

Q1 Strategy

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

As digital products became ubiquitous, the cultural heritage and creative sectors also stepped up to introduce new products. However, digital strategies are more than isolated digital products and the siloed processes behind them. Their role is to assess the impact of using technologies in different products and ensure these technologies are a means to a greater end instead of the sole drivers of digital transformations.

Innovation

Question 1

Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. What is the value proposition of your digital product(s), service(s) or offer(s)?

Tip: Invite participants to think about why digital offers and specific products are more than purely creative ambitions and how they can enhance the digital strategy and benefit stakeholders inside and outside their organisation.

2. What usually motivates the launch or update of digital product(s), service(s) or offer(s)?

Tip: Some examples of the possible motivations behind digital products are filling a market gap, opening new revenue streams or business models, expanding in new sectors, reaching new audiences, reducing costs, delivering existing services more efficiently, or strengthening relationships with audiences. The motivation behind each product or service, can also help the team identify the single, most important KPI (Key Performance Indicators) as an indicator of the success of a launch or update.

Innovation

Question 1

Guiding questions

3. What challenges or needs of new or existing audiences or internal stakeholders do you address with your digital product(s), service(s) or offer(s)?
4. What does your digital product's life cycle typically look like?

Innovation

Question 2

How does your organisation support digital innovation?

This question links to

Q3 Strategy

Q1+Q2 Skills

Q1+Q2 Organisation

2

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

Nowadays, digital innovation is key to any successful cultural organisation. But what organisations perceive as innovative can differ greatly. This is especially true in the museum sector, where there are no two institutions alike and where we oftentimes see vast gaps between the digital maturity and capacities of small and large museums.

However, an organisation that supports digital innovation typically offers its staff, contractors and audiences the opportunity to experiment with digital tools and fosters the delivery of digital content. It does so to create a bigger impact, either internally - improving the efficiency of departments and staff or de-siloing processes and information flows through the use of work management tools and applications (e.g., Trello or cloud-based conferencing tools such as Zoom), or externally - using digital products and services to increase their visibility, expand audiences or have a social impact on communities.

In both cases, digital innovation must be connected to strategic goals that go beyond mere technological advancement and speak of an organisation's wider mission.

Innovation

Question 2 Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. What would you define as innovative in your organisation?
2. What innovations would you like to see in your organisation in the future?
3. What are the first steps of developing experimental products, services, or ways of working?
4. Which applied research do you conduct before engaging in innovation?

Tip: *Some examples of applied research are audience research, market research, evaluation of activities, etc.*

Innovation

Question 2

Guiding questions

5. Do you seek strategic partnerships with innovative actors? Why? Why not?

Tip: Some examples of innovative actors are research organisations, other practitioners from the sector, universities, companies, experts, etc.

6. Have you ever applied for innovation funds? Why? Why not?

Openness

Question 1

How does your organisation show openness to synergies with external stakeholders and communities?

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

The openness of an organisation is often made apparent by opening-up activities (e.g., meaningful partnerships and exchanges with institutions in the same sector, accessing funding opportunities as a result of engaging with stakeholders, donors, partners in funding consortia). Furthermore, an organisation can open up towards audiences either by offering access and a platform for community groups deemed „voiceless“ or involving external actors (e.g., schools, youth groups, etc.) in co-creating exhibitions or cultural offers.

Openness (including open access) allows organisations to achieve important goals and can be transformative. Though museums, art organisations, libraries, science centres are open by definition, many institutions conflate openness with a wide and varied range of experiences or offers. In fact, openness is a highly engaging process that invites stakeholders to collaborate and co-create. Opening up thus, requires planning and commitment and can benefit from the use of digital tools.

Openness

Question 1 Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

Tip: Participants look back on a past opening-up activity. They can all choose the same activity or different ones. It's important to consider all activities that might have contributed to opening up to different actors, no matter how small.

1. Which departments, teams or staff members were involved in previous opening-up activities?
2. How did you decide on the type of opening-up activity?

Tip: Some opening-up activities are a one-off, typically centred around a theme, an exhibition, an event, or a historical milestone. Others can be recurrent, either part of a series or having several different iterations.

3. How did the public respond to the opening-up activity?

Tip: Consider the reasoning behind the chosen topic and type of activity chosen and reflect on whether it had the expected impact.

Openness

Question 1

Guiding questions

4. How was the impact of the opening-up activity measured?
5. What did you learn from the opening-up activity, and through what process?
6. What digital tools were used in this activity, and how did they help?

Tip: For example, using digital tools can help make communication and work processes more efficient, or facilitate the engagement and co-creation processes within a team and with audiences.

7. What might be other opening-up exercises that fit your organisation's culture?

Organisation

Question 1

How would you describe your leadership's attitude towards digital development?

This question links to

Q1 Skills

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

Developing digital capabilities under a strong digital leadership can lead to a more consistent and sustainable transformation. A person or department with both digital literacy and leadership skills are key to boosting the digital maturity of an institution. Such leadership can identify gaps in digital literacy as well as opportunities to expand the team's digital skills and knowledge and can play an essential role in empowering teams to become confident and imaginative when engaging with digital.

Organisation

Question 1 Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. Is there a dedicated person or department responsible for digital maturity in your organisation?

Tip: In case participants identify a lack of digital leadership within their organisation, they should think of an ideal future digital leadership and team structure (including the departments engaged in 'digital', dedicated resources/FTE, reporting hierarchy). They can also compare available, dedicated and required resources (both in-house and external), and explore things to consider when hiring new staff or accessing external capacities and partnerships (e.g., with universities, technical or software start-ups, domain experts, companies, museum, etc.).

2. How inclusive is the approach to digital development, and what improvements can be made?
3. What efforts does your organisation make to boost the digital capabilities of its staff?
4. How are the views of staff, audiences and stakeholders integrated into your organisation's approach to digital development?

Organisation

Question 2

How does your organisation align its digital development with its values and culture?

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

A comprehensive digital strategy must go beyond the quest for digital skills and innovation. Organisations that recognise how their values support their societal and ethical footprint and inscribe them in their digital strategy are more likely to sustain a digital development. Values meet digital development when, for example, organisations opt for digital solutions that do not have a significant environmental impact, or use CO2 emission standards (Greenhouse Gas Protocol, Creative Green Tool, etc.) to assess their ecological footprint. Imprinting a set of values on the digital development can also mean placing issues of diversity and inclusion at the core of the digital strategies. Furthermore, it can mean choosing to build synergies with ethically compatible stakeholders.

Organisation

Question 2

Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. How does your organisation define its values or culture?
2. How does your organisation share its set of values or culture with staff members and external stakeholders?
3. What is the process of aligning digital strategies with core values, and how could it be improved?
4. How does your organisation ensure partnerships are in line with its core values?

Skills

Question 1

How does your organisation seek to improve digital literacy and training opportunities?

This question links to

Q1 Organisation

Q2 Innovation

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

A strategy to boost digital skills is part and parcel of digital innovation. Digital skills have a knock-on effect on all aspects of an organisation and can be transformative. Such skills can help organisations attract wider, more diverse audiences and reinterpret their role in society. Moreover, acquiring digital skills increases confidence and empowers staff members. This is especially true for those involved in transferring collections online, interacting with the public and collaborating with others within the organisation and beyond.

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. What would you consider as signs that an organisation values digital literacy?

Tip: Also consider the broader networks or associations your organisation is part of, or other ways it keeps up to date with the latest trends and tools.

2. How does your organisation support the digital training of its staff?

Tip: Expand on existing and desired training materials, activities (incl. resources and frequency) and who they target. Think about relevant networks, resources and open access platforms already in use that are beneficial to building digital literacy. Consider yours and other staff's career development opportunities.

Skills

Question 1 Guiding questions

Question 1

Guiding questions

3. How do you wish your organisation supported the digital training of its staff?
4. How could you and your colleagues make the case for more digital training?
5. How does your organisation encourage knowledge exchange and peer-to-peer learning internally and with other organisations?

Skills

Question 2

How does your organisation promote the acquisition of digital skills in the community?

Setting the context

Set the tone for the self-reflection by giving participants some context.

Digital skills play a significant role in creativity, artistic design, and cultural appreciation. Lately, museums and other cultural organisations have ramped up their efforts to cultivate digital skills in their communities. By investing in communities, an organisation can attract wider audiences and foster the production of valuable creative output, that could then be exhibited and/or acquired.

Question 2

Guiding questions

Tips for self-reflection

Give participants a few tips before they proceed to answer the questions.

1. What would you consider signs that your organisation promotes or values the acquisition of digital skills in the community?
2. How is the acquisition of digital skills in the community supported through your organisation's programmes and offers?

Tip: Think of the websites, platforms or online resources your organisation uses to promote 'digital' to communities/audiences and your organisation's aspirations when it comes to co-creation or consultation with peers and/or audiences.

3. How is the acquisition of digital skills in the community supported through your organisation's partnerships and networking activities?

	Front side	Back side
	<p>1</p> <h2>Strategy</h2> Q1 Innovation 	
MAIN QUESTION		<p>Digital Incubator for Museums</p> <p>DOORS</p>

1

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

Who was involved in setting up a digital strategy for your organisation?

1

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

How is the digital strategy used, and by whom?

1

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the focus of your digital strategy?
Why?

1

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

How is the digital strategy designed in terms of objectives, planning, and actions?

1

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

How is the digital strategy designed in terms of decision-making and allocating resources?

1

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the time span of your digital strategy, and how often is it revised?

Front side

Back side

2

Strategy

How does your organisation identify the biggest challenges to boosting digital maturity?

MAIN QUESTION

Digital Incubator for Museums

DOORS

This question links to

Q1 Organisation

Q1 Skills

2

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

What are the steps in identifying challenges to digital maturity?

2

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

What tools or processes do you use to identify challenges?

<p data-bbox="629 778 1081 1023">Who is involved in setting up, running and revising the process of identifying challenges?</p>	
<p data-bbox="501 692 546 1091">GUIDING QUESTION</p>	<h2 data-bbox="1384 309 1617 363">Strategy</h2> <p data-bbox="1305 778 1704 1075">Which external factors do you perceive as threatening and/or enabling digital maturity?</p>

	Front side	Back side
	<p>3</p> <h2>Strategy</h2> <p>Q2 Innovation</p> 	
MAIN QUESTION	Digital Incubator for Museums	
	DOORS	

3

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

How are IT services managed?

3

Strategy

GUIDING QUESTION

How does your organisation ensure secure data management?

GUIDING QUESTION

3

Strategy

Do you follow metadata standards, and if not, why?

GUIDING QUESTION

3

Strategy

Which standards do you deem essential for future digital products or services?

	Front side		Back side
	<p>1</p> <h1>Innovation</h1> <p>Q1 Strategy</p>		

1

Innovation

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the value proposition of your digital product(s), service(s) or offer(s)?

1

Innovation

GUIDING QUESTION

What usually motivates the launch or update of digital product(s), service(s) or offer(s)?

1

Innovation

GUIDING QUESTION

What challenges or needs of new or existing audiences or internal stakeholders do you address with your digital product(s), service(s) or offer(s)?

1

Innovation

GUIDING QUESTION

What does your digital product's life cycle typically look like?

	Front side	Back side
2	<h2>Innovation</h2> <p>Q1+Q2 Skills</p>	
MAIN QUESTION		<p>Digital Incubator for Museums</p> <p>DOORS</p>

2

Innovation

What would you define as innovative in your organisation?

GUIDING QUESTION

2

Innovation

What innovations would you like to see in your organisation in the future?

GUIDING QUESTION

2

Innovation

What are the first steps of developing experimental products, services, or ways of working?

GUIDING QUESTION

2

Innovation

Which applied research do you conduct before engaging in innovation?

GUIDING QUESTION

2

Innovation

GUIDING QUESTION

Do you seek strategic partnerships with innovative actors?
Why? Why not?

2

Innovation

GUIDING QUESTION

Have you ever applied for innovation funds?
Why? Why not?

Front side

Back side

1

Openness

How does your organisation show openness to synergies with external stakeholders and communities?

MAIN QUESTION

Digital Incubator
for Museums

D D RS

1
GUIDING QUESTION

Openness

Which departments, teams or staff members were involved in previous opening-up activities?

1
GUIDING QUESTION

Openness

How did you decide on the type of opening-up activity?

1
GUIDING QUESTION

Openness

How did the public respond to the opening-up activity?

1

Openness

GUIDING QUESTION

How was the impact of the opening-up activity measured?

1

Openness

GUIDING QUESTION

What did you learn from the opening-up activity, and through what process?

1

Openness

GUIDING QUESTION

What digital tools were used in this activity, and how did they help?

1

Openness

GUIDING QUESTION

What might be other opening-up exercises that fit your organisation's culture?

Front side

Back side

1

Organisation

MAIN QUESTION

How would you describe your leadership's attitude towards digital development?

Digital Incubator
for Museums
DOORS

This question links to

Q1 Skills

1

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

Is there a dedicated person or department responsible for digital maturity in your organisation?

1

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

How inclusive is the approach to digital development, and what improvements can be made?

1

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

What efforts does your organisation make to boost the digital capabilities of its staff?

1

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

How are the views of staff, audiences and stakeholders integrated into your organisation's approach to digital development?

Front side

Back side

2

Organisation

MAIN QUESTION

How does your organisation align its digital development with its values and culture?

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Digital Incubator
for Museums

2

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

How does your organisation define its values or culture?

2

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

How does your organisation share its set of values or culture with staff members and external stakeholders?

2

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the process of aligning digital strategies with core values, and how could it be improved?

2

Organisation

GUIDING QUESTION

How does your organisation ensure partnerships are in line with its core values?

	Front side	Back side
	<p>1</p> <h2>Skills</h2> Q2 Innovation 	
MAIN QUESTION		

1

Skills

What would you consider as signs that an organisation values digital literacy?

GUIDING QUESTION

1

Skills

How does your organisation support the digital training of its staff?

GUIDING QUESTION

1

Skills

How do you wish your organisation supported the digital training of its staff?

GUIDING QUESTION

1

Skills

GUIDING QUESTION

How could you and your colleagues make the case for more digital training?

1

Skills

GUIDING QUESTION

How does your organisation encourage knowledge exchange and peer-to-peer learning internally and with other organisations?

	Front side	Back side
	<p>2</p> <h2>Skills</h2>	

2

Skills

GUIDING QUESTION

What would you consider signs that your organisation promotes or values the acquisition of digital skills in the community?

2

Skills

GUIDING QUESTION

How is the acquisition of digital skills in the community supported through your organisation's programmes and offers?

2

Skills

GUIDING QUESTION

How is the acquisition of digital skills in the community supported through your organisation's partnerships and networking activities?